

Air Pollution: Neurological Diseases and Need for Technology to Reduce the Burden

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ABSTRACT

Air pollution is known to cause neuroinflammation, reactive oxygen species (ROS), and neuropathology instigating central nervous system (CNS) disease. Stroke incidence and Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease pathology are linked to air pollution. Recent reports reveal that air pollution components reach the brain. Further, systemic effects known to impact lung and cardiovascular disease also impinge upon CNS health. While mechanisms driving air pollution-induced CNS pathology are poorly understood, new evidence suggests that activation of microglia and changes in the blood-brain barrier may be critical to this process. Here, we summarize recent findings detailing the mechanisms through which air pollution reaches the brain and activates the resident innate immune response to become a chronic source of pro-inflammatory factors and ROS culpable in CNS disease.

INTRODUCTION

Air pollution is one of the top ten leading causes of death, accounting for 12.5% of all fatalities worldwide, as per National Institute of Environmental Health Sciences (NIEHS) data. Out of these air-pollution-related fatalities, the majority (>50%) can be attributed to indoor air pollution (IAP). The increase in urbanization has resulted in an ongoing epidemic of polluted air in most countries.

Studies have shown that exposure to high levels of air pollutants results in respiratory and cardiovascular morbidity and mortality; however, ongoing research has shown that the central nervous system (CNS) may also be at risk of harmful effects from exposure to high levels of air pollutants.

The authors would like to bring to attention two main pathways for air contaminants such as particulate matter (PM), especially PM2.5 and PM10, ozone (O3), nitrogen dioxide (NO2), sulfur dioxide (SO2), and organic and inorganic carbon nanoparticles to enter the neurological system and cause neuroinflammation leading to neuronal death as seen in figure 1.

- Nasal route:
 - Olfactory bulb pathway
 - Retrograde neuronal transport via the trigeminal nerve
- Respiratory system:
 - Direct entrance into the bloodstream
 - Retrograde neuronal transport via the vagus nerve
 - Local inflammation can lead to systemic inflammation and the production of cytokines that disrupt the blood-brain barrier

Air pollutants in the brain trigger the innate immune response, which can produce a steady stream of pro-inflammatory cytokines like tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNFα), Interleukin-1 beta (IL-1β), Interleukin-6 (IL-6), and reactive oxygen species (ROS). This then activates microglial cells, which in turn cause neuroinflammation: lipid peroxidation, dopaminergic neurotoxicity, astrogliosis, and protein aggregation, leading to neuronal death and neurodegenerative diseases such as Parkinson's disease and Alzheimer's disease.

METHODOLOGY

This is a literature review poster to investigate and assess the current knowledge on the repercussions of air pollution on the central nervous system. The research design method is a scientific evidence-based rapid review. Standard literature and database searches were implemented, and relevant material was gathered and extracted information evaluated. Tables were adapted from literature and conceptualized to fit the flow.

Figure 1: Pathogenesis of air pollutants mediated by different mechanisms. © 2009 Elsevier Ltd. All rights reserved. (Block & Calderón-Garcidueñas, 2009)

DISCUSSION

In this section, we discuss different epidemiological and experimental study designs (table 1) that have demonstrated alterations to the nervous system and the consequences of air pollution-induced neurodegenerative changes and neurotoxicity.

- Particulate Matter: It consists of a complex mixture suspended in the air that includes solid and liquid components. It is the most harmful pollutant on a global scale and affects more people than other pollutants. It has been demonstrated that exposure to PM2.5, PM10, SO2, and NO2 together reduces the expression of the apoptosis genes (p53, Bax, and BCL-2), which may result in neuropathic changes, memory issues, and issues with spatial orientation.
- Ozone (O3): Ozone exposure can cause lipid peroxidation in the brain, neuronal death in the substantia nigra, and thus motor disorders and memory loss. Ozone can affect the immune system, irritate mucous membranes, change the concentrations of neurotransmitters like serotonin and increase the risk of suicide. It also interferes with the circadian cycle by altering melatonin secretion/production, decreasing cognitive function, decreasing motor activity, and other neuronal dysfunction, in addition to producing epigenetic effects in humans.
- Nano-sized carbon particles: Nanoparticles are highly potent and potentially lethal; they can increase mRNA expressions of IL-1β, TNF-α and Chemokine ligand 2, 3 (CCL2, CCL3) in the olfactory bulb, which can disrupt the integrity of BBB. These nanoparticles can also increase the extracellular level of glutamate and glycine levels. Studies have also shown a decrease in exploratory behavior, microglial activation, and neuronal damage.

Pollutant model	Experiment model	Tests / Assays	Primary findings
Particulate matter	Mouse	Tyrosine hydroxylase immunostaining	Dopaminergic neurotoxicity Astrogliosis
	Rat	IHC, RT-PCR	Increased TNFα and IL-1 α levels
Ozone	Rat	Behavioral test	Impaired olfactory perception and social recognition memory
	Rat	Lipid peroxidation assay	Increased lipid peroxidation
	Rat	Immunohistochemistry	Increased c-Fos expression in different brain regions, including nucleus tractus solitarius
Nanoparticles (nanosized carbon black)	Mouse	Open-field test	Decreased exploratory behavior
	Cell Culture	In-vitro	Microglial Activation, Neuron Damage

Table 1: Pollutant and experiment models

About 5% of the total population globally is affected by depressive disorders. Per a study an increase of just 10g/m3 of PM2.5, can increase the risk of a depressive episode. Certain substances are linked to higher rates of depression. The effects of melatonin, escitalopram, and desipramine are highly reduced in the presence of ozone. Lipid peroxidation in the brain is caused due to ozone exposure, which in turn leads to neuronal death in the substantia nigra, thereby causing memory loss and motor disorders.

CONCLUSIONS / POLICY DIRECTIONS

The authors would highlight a few policy-related points that should be implemented to reduce the burden of air pollution and pollutants on harmful effects on the central nervous system.

- Indoor air quality monitoring needs to be done and improved with the help of HVAC systems but also be supplemented with the use of state-of-the-art air filtration and purification devices
- Epidemiologists should identify deaths from air pollution for feasible evidence to be presented to policymakers to produce tangible results to create efforts against reducing the harmful effects of air pollution
- Educational initiatives need to be formulated and implemented
- Vehicle-free days need to be encouraged in cities
- Reducing wood and solid fuels and replacement with cleaner fuels such as compressed natural gas indoors should be encouraged and adopted on a mass scale in low and middle-income countries
- Projects that limit emissions should be applied thoughtfully, as these could reduce cognitive disorders
- Primary health care services must have a full prenatal and postnatal environmental and occupational background of indoor and outdoor chemical threats and preventive and mitigation steps.
- In populations exposed to large amounts of air contaminants, identifying people at risk for cognitive deficits, brain structural/volumetric, and neurodegenerative accelerating changes should be prioritized

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Flowchart 1: Biosensors: Components and principal attributes needed

Environmental biosensors need to be manufactured by utilizing superior characteristics of nanomaterials and novel nanocomposites to focus on in-situ and real-time monitoring of pollutants. High-efficiency particulate air filters (HEPA) trap impurities as they pass through the filter and filters using photo electrochemical oxidation (PECO) technology are known to destroy, rather than trap, the impurities. One of the newer detection and filtration systems includes a HEPA filter with PECO, which breaks down pollutants by using free radicals, thus enabling the detection and destruction of pollutants.